

ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION MECHANISM OF VALUE ADDED TAX.

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Abstract: Value added tax is a fiscal burden. This rate encourages workers to work harder and earn more, to increase labor productivity. Currently, the purpose of using such a rate is to curb monetary inflation, strengthen money circulation and provide a significant income to the budget.

Key words: turnover, compliance, inflation rate, secret economy.

Currently, in the practice of taxation, various methods can be used to calculate the value added tax. Two of them require calculation of value added tax from a predetermined amount of value added or calculation from its individual elements. This method is a direct method, in which value added tax is calculated as a percentage of the estimated value of goods and services. In the direct method, there can be two options: 1) the way to separate the value of material assets from the income after the sale of products 2) by adding separate value-added elements.

Value-added tax is a form of increasing values that are partially increased at the market stages of production, that is, at the stages from raw materials to consumer goods. Value added tax is charged on all sales invoices. In theory, its object is added value. The added value, in turn, is the remaining part of the value of the product after deducting the raw materials, materials, semi-finished products and other expenses consumed in its production. It also includes value added, wages, social security contributions, profits, interest on loans, advertising costs, transportation, electricity, and more.

It should be recognized that the method of calculating value added tax is widely used in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This method is called the accounting method or compensation method, and its calculation is carried out by dividing the amount of value-added tax from the amount received from the realization of the value of the assets obtained for consumption in production. When using the accounting method, only the difference between the above two values is paid to the budget. In the declaration submitted to the tax authorities, together with other mandatory information, two main calculations of value added tax are presented, that is, the total amount of the realized product and the total value of the purchased goods and services.

They are value added tax collectors, and the movement of goods is calculated by sales clerks at each stage. When buying goods for production, the seller does not take any economic responsibility, because he receives from the state the amount necessary to cover the tax, this amount is paid by the buyer, except for the tax payment on the sale of the product. The essence of this mechanism is that the tax is paid by the end consumer. Therefore, value added tax is an indirect (indirect) tax and the responsibility for it is on the consumer's side.

One of the important and basic conditions for solving the task of transition to value added tax is its expediency and effectiveness of this change in the tax system.

Currently, value added tax is applied in more than 60 countries of the world. In many cases, the government does not introduce this type of tax in an unstable situation in the country. For example, this type of tax was introduced in France in the 50s. During this period, the deficit in the country's consumer market was completely eliminated. Because the government realized that the introduction of value added tax during the period of shortage of consumer goods would cause hyperinflation.

Thus, the analysis shows that value added tax is the most fiscal (treasury) tax in the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is necessary to pay it and it is impossible to "escape" this type of tax. In addition, this type of tax protects the budget from excess

expenditures in inflationary conditions. Value added tax was introduced in the context of high inflation and increased budget revenues after the liberalization of prices. Therefore, its introduction was appropriate.

The experience of the countries of the world shows that in the transition to the market economy, 25-40% of the gross national product created in the country corresponds to the contribution of the informal economy, the main part of which remains untaxed. In our opinion, the only way to regulate them at a time when hufiya has a large contribution to the economy is a value added tax. Therefore, one of the main tasks in the current period is to preserve the value added tax. In addition, the main part of the income of the budget corresponds to this type of tax.

After the introduction of value added tax in the tax system, it was found that its legal base was not completely improved. This point requires a number of changes to the rules of the tax collection procedure.

Since the introduction of value added tax, its rate has changed several times. Initially, its size was 30%, but in most countries its size was somewhat lower, taking into account the equality of the environment, since 1993 the tax rates were reduced to 20%, and for food products to 10%. This situation, in turn, had a negative impact on the income part of the budget. As a result, he began to demand a return to slightly higher rates of taxation. For this purpose, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a special decree to support important areas of macroeconomics. In accordance with the decree, the payers of the indirect (indirect) tax, its objects, procedure and term are determined by the "Tax Code", and it is noted that this type of tax is hidden and has the character of an extraordinary tax.

Some practitioners deny that value added tax is "harmful". According to them, previously turnover tax was charged at each stage of production, and value added tax is a "reckoned" tax. Their perception that working capital will leave production is not related to the tax rate, but to the amount of tax paid by the suppliers of the goods. Advocates of this side of the issue ignore the need to improve the value added

tax. But they base their opinion on the results of the practice of reducing the rate of value added tax, which they followed before.

Changes in the value added tax rate since its introduction. (as a percentage)

Countries	Initial standard rate	Current rate
Austria	16	20
Belgium	18	20,5
Canada	7	7
Denmark	10	25
Finland	11.1	22
France	20	20,6
Germany	10	16
Greece	16	18
Iceland	22	24,5
Ireland	16,4	21
Italy	12	19
Japan	3	6
Luxembourg	8	15
Mexico	10	10
Average rate	12,6	17,1

Many of the critics of the proposals of the tax authorities point out that the experience of reducing the value added tax does not give positive results. Based on their logic, the reduction of value added tax rates is the reason for the reduction of budget revenue.

One of the important features of the method of accounting in the system of payment of value added tax is that the amount of value added tax received and paid largely depends on the use of this method.

Therefore, the tax curve on gross income requires an evaluation from the point of view of fairness, while keeping one type of (indirect) taxes (excise duty and VAT). However, it should be noted that in many western countries, VAT and gross income tax are not collected at the same time.

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